

HYDROGEN PRODUCTION BY WATER SPLITTING USING NANO ZrO₂ AND NANO TiO₂

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The hydrogen was produced using two catalysts *i.e.* n-ZrO₂ and n-TiO₂. The experiments were carried out in n-ZrO₂ + H₂O_{ads.}, n-ZrO₂ + H₂O_{liq.}, n-TiO₂ + H₂O_{ads.}, and n-TiO₂ + H₂O_{liq.} systems. All the experiments were carried out at 300 K temperature at D= 1.42 Gy/s. The results of these findings are discussed below. For this comparison, the n-ZrO₂ + H₂O_{ads.} system was compared with the n-TiO₂ + H₂O_{ads.} system. Similarly, n-ZrO₂ + H₂O_{liq.} system was compared with n-TiO₂ + H₂O_{liq.} system. For the comparison of the n-ZrO₂ + H₂O_{ads.} system with the n-TiO₂ + H₂O_{ads.} system. A perusal of these indicates that the maximum hydrogen was produced at 80 and 8 hrs in n-ZrO₂ + H₂O_{ads.} and n-TiO₂ + H₂O_{ads.} systems. The amounts of hydrogen produced were 7.0 x 10¹⁷ and 2.21 x 10¹⁶ molecules. The experimental time difference to obtain maximum hydrogen was 1:10 in n-TiO₂ and n-ZrO₂ catalysts. The amount of hydrogen produced was 31.67 times higher with n-TiO₂ compared to n-ZrO₂ catalyst. It clearly indicated that n-TiO₂ was a better catalyst than n-ZrO₂. For the comparison of the n-ZrO₂ + H₂O_{liq.} system with the n-TiO₂ + H₂O_{liq.} system. A perusal of these table indicates that the maximum hydrogen was produced at 60 and 6 hrs in n-ZrO₂ + H₂O_{liq.} and n-TiO₂ + H₂O_{liq.} systems. The amounts of hydrogen produced were 140.0 x 10¹⁷ and 80.0 x 10¹⁶ molecules. The experimental time difference to obtain maximum hydrogen was 1:10 in n-TiO₂ and n-ZrO₂ catalysts. The amount of hydrogen produced was 17.5 times higher with n-TiO₂ compared to n-ZrO₂ catalyst. It clearly indicated that n-TiO₂ was a better catalyst than n-ZrO₂. When comparing n-TiO₂ and n-ZrO₂ as catalysts for water splitting in hydrogen production, several factors make n-TiO₂ generally more favourable. The most important are as discussed below. It is very important to determine the amount of hydrogen produced per gram catalyst per second [W(H₂), molecules/g.s] and the total number of molecular hydrogen generated per 100 eV [G(H₂), molecules/100 eV]. The values in W(H₂) in ZrO₂ + H₂O_{ads.}, ZrO₂ + H₂O_{liq.}, TiO₂ + H₂O_{ads.} and TiO₂ + H₂O_{liq.} systems were 4.44 x 10¹³, 2.78 x 10¹⁴, 1.38 x 10¹³ and 4.2 x 10¹³ molecules/g.s. The values in G(H₂) in ZrO₂ + H₂O_{ads.}, ZrO₂ + H₂O_{liq.}, TiO₂ + H₂O_{ads.} and TiO₂ + H₂O_{liq.} systems were 2.14, 13.5, 0.16 and 0.48 molecules/100eV (Table). Table clearly show that molecular hydrogen amounts in the n-ZrO₂+H₂O_{liq.} system was 6.0 to 6.5 times higher than in n-ZrO₂ +H₂O_{ads.} system. The molecular hydrogen content in the n-TiO₂+H₂O_{liq.} system was 2.5 to 3.0 times higher than in the case of the n-TiO₂+H₂O_{ads.} system. The rates and radiation-chemical yields of molecular hydrogen are given in Table. The increase in G(H₂) values observed during water radiolysis in the presence of n-ZrO₂ and n-TiO₂ compared to the yield observed during radiolysis of pure water can be attributed to two factors: the creation of active water decomposition centres on the surface of n-ZrO₂ and n-TiO₂ under the influence of γ -quanta of δ -electrons and secondary radiation from these substances [1-2].

Table: The process rates and hydrogen amounts produced during radiation-heterogeneous radiolysis in different systems.

Process systems with Temp	W(H ₂), molecules, g ⁻¹ ·s ⁻¹	G(H ₂), molecules/100eV
ZrO ₂ + H ₂ O _{ads} , 300 K	4.44 x 10 ¹³	2.14
ZrO ₂ + H ₂ O _{liq} , 300 K	2.78 x 10 ¹⁴	13.5
TiO ₂ + H ₂ O _{ads} , 300 K	1.38 x 10 ¹³	0.16
TiO ₂ + H ₂ O _{liq} , 300 K	4.2 x 10 ¹³	0.48

It is clear from the Table that the amounts of hydrogen production increased a little bit in both systems. An augment of hydrogen production from 140.0×10^{17} to 144.8×10^{17} was observed in n-ZrO₂ + H₂O_{liq} system. Also, an augment of hydrogen production from 8.0×10^{17} to 8.63×10^{17} was observed in n-TiO₂ + H₂O_{liq} system. These amounts of hydrogen increase were not considered significant and were ignored due to experimental complexity and experimental cost. There are two studies in this article *i.e.* hydrogen production by water splitting in radiolysis and the structural changes in the phot-catalysts (n-ZrO₂ and n-TiO₂ nanoparticles). Good amounts of hydrogen have been produced by both the photo-catalyst with a maximum yield of 140.0×10^{17} molecules/g with the n-ZrO₂-H₂O_{liq} system. The kinetics of hydrogen production at gamma radiolysis of water and n-ZrO₂+H₂O and n-TiO₂+H₂O systems were investigated. It is established that the radiation-chemical yield for n-ZrO₂+H₂O and n-TiO₂+H₂O systems is more ($G(H_2)=2.14 - 0.16$ molecule/100 eV) than at radiolysis of pure water ($G(H_2)=0.45$ molecule/100 eV). The structural changes showed a monoclinic structure (space group P 21/c) of the initial sample and after gamma irradiation, the structure changed to triclinic (space group P1). Contrarily, there was no change in the structure of n-TiO₂ nanoparticles after gamma radiation irradiation. The effect of sodium chloride in water on hydrogen production was studied; showing a slight increase in hydrogen production. The article's scientific section is interesting since it discusses how to produce hydrogen from water splitting and how gamma radiation can alter the structural properties of titanium and zirconium oxide. These studies are useful in developing green energy (hydrogen) and space missions, nuclear reactors, and other high-radiation settings (nano-ZrO₂ structural changes) [3-4].

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